

INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF GEOGRAPHY EDUCATION AND DEVELOPING THE COMPETENCE OF PUPILS BASED ON A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH

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Abstract. The article examines issues of increasing the effectiveness of geography education and developing pupils' competencies based on a competency-based approach.

Key words: modern pedagogical technology, communicative competence, competence in working with information, self-development competence, socially active civic competence, national and general cultural competence, mathematical literacy, competence in being aware of and using innovations in science and technology.

Introduction. At present, due to the introduction of modern pedagogical technologies into the educational process, there is a need to develop modern approaches to the use of educational tools, including information educational environments, in the process of teaching and upbringing geography in general education schools. Because with the help of informational educational environments, it is possible to figuratively present geographical knowledge and effectively organise the process of independent learning of pupils. When fully conveying the topics of the content of the subject "Geography of Karakalpakstan" to the consciousness of pupils in general education schools, didactic teaching aids placed in information educational environments, including interactive maps, multimedia applications, presentations on the topic, virtual educational technologies, video lessons, video clips, online non-standard, open, closed and PISA tests, various crosswords are used, the motivation of pupils in the subject increases even more, they understand certain geographical problems, easily assimilate the planned knowledge in the textbook, serve as an important pedagogical tool for the formation of geographical imagination and orientation towards independent learning. The use of multimedia applications and interactive teaching aids in geography education has a number of advantages over printed visual aids. In traditional visual aids, the pupil has the opportunity to simultaneously see the entire structure of the phenomenon or process [3; 208-p].

Through the use of multimedia, interactive visual aids, it is possible to view the process and phenomenon at any time, in order to more fully explain any part or phenomenon, their demonstration several times [4; - 70 p].

Therefore, there is a need to develop a holistic mechanism for using information educational environments in geography lessons. To develop this mechanism, it is necessary for the teacher to redesign improved teaching methods, means, and forms of conveying the content of the topic studied in the lesson to the consciousness of pupils using advanced pedagogical technologies and pedagogical software tools of computers, as well as to design the structure and content of the organization of their pedagogical activity [2; 62-p].

Main part. In this regard, when teaching the subject of geography of Karakalpakstan in general education schools, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

- analysis of the purpose, content of the lesson and the logic of studying the material;
- thorough preparation of educational and control materials on the topic;
- identification of the main rules (evidence, hypotheses) that pupils should study, development of the necessary didactic material;
- correct selection of necessary teaching aids in accordance with the objectives of the lesson;
- it is necessary to develop methods for using the selected teaching aids. At the same time, it is necessary to pay attention to:
 - selection of teaching methods and information educational resources based on the nature of the topics covered;
 - development of stages of organizing classes based on the mutual integration of teaching methods and digital learning tools;
 - improvement of mechanisms for using standard and non-standard online tests in assessing pupils' knowledge.

The above recommendations serve as the main source for the teacher's effective organization of the geography educational process.

In teaching the subject "Geography of Karakalpakstan," along with providing pupils with educational, upbringing, and developmental education, it is advisable to apply the acquired theoretical knowledge in practice, that is, to form educational competence. Therefore, competence should be understood as the ability of learners to apply existing knowledge, skills, and abilities in their daily activities. Also, based on the continuity, consistency of education, the priority of the learner's personality and interests, the following basic competencies are formed in accordance with their age characteristics. Depending on the nature of competence formation, basic competence and subject-specific competencies are used.

These competencies are formed in pupils through the teaching of the subject "Geography of Karakalpakstan." Furthermore, based on the content of the subject, general competencies related to the subject are also formed in pupils. When teaching the subject "Geography of Karakalpakstan," the following types of subject competencies are formed in pupils:

- Competence in observing, identifying, understanding, and explaining natural, socio-economic processes and phenomena;
- Competence in the correct use of geographical objects, place names;
- Competence in the practical use of globes, geographical atlases and maps;
- Competence in environmental protection and ecological culture;

Pupils of the subject "Geography of Karakalpakstan" should have the necessary and sufficient level of preparedness, as well as the following competencies in the competence of observing, identifying, understanding, and explaining natural, socio-economic processes and phenomena.

As a result of studying the subject of Physical geography of Karakalpakstan:

- can describe the geographical location, geological structure, relief features, and distribution of mineral types of the territory;
- Observes and can independently describe natural processes and geographical phenomena occurring in the territory of Karakalpakstan;
- observes the climatic features of the region, the change of seasons, and can describe the natural changes associated with them;
- in everyday life determines changes in the weather in their place of residence based on local indicators, can measure air temperature using a thermometer;
- can characterize climate change and the factors affecting it by determining the directions of the horizon using a compass and local symbols;
- knows and can tell about the nature of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and its natural geographical regions;
- can perform measurements and determinations of natural phenomena and processes in the territory in everyday life using various instruments (compass, thermometer, barometer, weather vane, etc.);
- Can characterize the natural conditions and resources of Karakalpakstan, analyze and compare their territorial features;
- Knows, understands, and can explain with examples the main geographical factors and patterns that determine the diversity of the nature of Karakalpakstan;
- can describe the geography of the internal waters of the territory (rivers, lakes, irrigation networks) and their changes in accordance with the climate;

- describes the protection of the soil, flora, fauna, and nature of Karakalpakstan, determines the names of specially protected areas and measures for their organisation.

Conclusion. In the 7th grade of general education schools, the course of physical geography of Karakalpakstan is studied consistently. In the course of studying this course, pupils will learn about the peculiarities of the nature of Karakalpakstan in the part of physical geography and its commonalities with the Central Asian region. In this case, along with describing the components of nature, their economic significance, natural and anthropogenic complexes, competencies in the use and protection of nature, and ecological problems are formed.

In addition, it is established that "knowledge aimed at ecology and environmental protection" should be integrated into the content of the geography subject in grades V-VII [1.1], and the above-mentioned goals and objectives, based on the natural conditions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, primarily require the inclusion of a sufficient amount of knowledge and skills related to ecology, nature management, and environmental protection in the curricula and textbooks of geography education in general education schools.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022, No. UP-60 "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026".
2. Dauletbayev O.U. Economic location and natural resources of Kongirot and Muynak district. "Экономика и социум" №11(126) 2024 www.iupr.ru.
3. Safarov U.X. Talabalarning bilim faolligini oshirish jarayonida EHMdan foydalanish (O'zbekiston tabiiy jo'g'rofiyasi fani misolida): ped. fan. nom. diss. – T.: 1994. -141 b.
4. Ахаян А.А. Теория и практика становления дистанционного педагогического образования: автор. дис. док. пед. наук. Улан-У де., 2001. – 23 с.